

THE INFLUENCE OF PERFORMANCE ALLOWANCES AND JOB SATISFACTION ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE THROUGH INTRINSIC MOTIVATION IN EMPLOYEES OF THE INDONESIAN MIGRANT WORKER PROTECTION AGENCY (BP2MI)

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Abstract: *This research aims to determine and analyze the influence of 1) performance allowances and job satisfaction on intrinsic motivation, 2) performance allowances and job satisfaction on performance, 3) intrinsic motivation on performance, 4) performance allowances on employee performance through intrinsic motivation, 5) job satisfaction influences employee performance through intrinsic motivation. The research was conducted at the Indonesian Migrant Worker Protection Agency (BP2MI) with a research sample of 85 respondents. The sampling technique uses a simple random sampling technique. The data analysis method uses descriptive analysis and path analysis.*

The results of the research show that: 1) there is a positive and significant influence of performance allowances and job satisfaction on intrinsic motivation, 2) there is a positive and significant influence of performance allowances and job satisfaction on performance, 3) there is a positive and significant influence of intrinsic motivation on performance, 4) there is a positive and significant effect of performance allowances on employee performance through intrinsic motivation, 5) there is no positive and significant effect of job satisfaction on employee performance through intrinsic motivation.

Keywords: *Performance Allowances, Job Satisfaction, Intrinsic Motivation, Employee Performance.*

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Introduction

Human resources play a very important role in determining the progress of an organization or organization. According to Voon et al. (2011), human resources are the most important assets for an organization and an organization must have leaders who can lead and motivate employees to achieve organizational goals. Human resources must play an active role and have high competence to achieve organizational goals. Mohammad et al (2010) stated that the level of success of an organization can be seen from the performance of the organization in managing the resources it has. Organizations with good performance have effectiveness in handling their human resources and determining targets that must be achieved both individually and as an organization.

Moreover, in the era of globalization, the world is increasingly in our grasp, causing the paradigm of life to become more modern, forcing all lines to continue to make changes according to the dynamics that occur. No exception for organizations or organizations, both private and government must

be ready for uncertain strategic environmental changes. As one of the Non-Departmental Government Institutions that handles the protection and placement of Indonesian migrant workers abroad, the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI) is also required to change its mindset to follow the development of an era that is increasingly open to serving the community, especially job seekers abroad.

To serve the community seeking work abroad well, BP2MI employees are required to have high loyalty, morality and militancy in their work. An employee, to achieve optimal performance, needs to foster a motivation that can trigger him to work optimally and achieve organizational goals effectively and efficiently. Achievement of goals can vary due to different individual behaviors. Some factors that cause differences in behavior include the perception, attitude, and personality of each individual. Every employee in achieving organizational goals will have feelings of satisfaction and dissatisfaction in working.

Therefore, there needs to be an ethically healthy organization for employees created in an organization, where job satisfaction is an important thing for every employee in the organization. As part of the government apparatus organization, the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI) which serves prospective workers who want to work abroad, is required to provide high public service performance. This high service performance is obtained from the performance of quality and solid human resources. Building a high-performance and solid team requires awareness of the roles and responsibilities of each member, this awareness can be built if their job satisfaction can be achieved properly.

Performance is a very important and interesting part because it has proven to be very important, an institution wants employees to work hard according to their abilities to achieve good work results, without good performance from all employees, success in achieving goals will be difficult to achieve. Performance includes mental attitudes and behaviors that always have the view that the work carried out at this time must be of better quality than the implementation of past work, for the future to be of better quality than at this time. An employee or employee will feel proud and satisfied with the achievements achieved based on the performance given to the organization. Good performance is a desired condition in the world of work. An employee will get good work performance if his performance is following standards, both quality and quantity.

Employee performance can be seen from the level of employee discipline. Performance is a function of motivation, skills, and role perception (Stoner, 1989). In addition, Bernardin and Russel (1993) state that performance is the achievement of results obtained from certain job functions or activities during a certain period. Handoko (2008) states that performance is the process by which organizations evaluate or assess employee work performance. Suntoro (Tika, 2006) stated that performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization to achieve organizational goals within a certain period. According to Simamora (2004), performance refers to the level of achievement of tasks that form an employee's job. Tika (2006) defines performance as the result of a person's or group's job function/activity in an organization that is influenced by various factors to achieve organizational goals within a certain period.

Performance assessment is "a system through which organizations evaluate or assess employee performance in accordance with their respective performance to the organization" (Handoko, 2008). This system aims to motivate employees to improve performance. Therefore, good performance is not only beneficial to individuals, but institutional institutions or organizations and the community will also benefit. This shows that the use of information systems in organizations or institutional institutions is very much needed. One of them is research concerning employee performance which is believed to be one of the keys to success in the organization.

Benefits include remuneration that can affect the rise and fall of employee work performance, and influence work decisions and employee motivation. So the arrangement of benefits must be truly fair and proper. The main purpose of providing or providing this type of benefit often called "Fringe Benefit" is to retain

employees in the long term. The basic premise of any welfare benefits program is that employees value employees and want to work for extra money to gain a better life. This is based on the assumption that money is the strongest motivation. Therefore, the government or organization must do several things that can increase employee work productivity.

To encourage higher work productivity, the government or organization that adopt a welfare allowance system that covers all aspects desired and expected by employees as part of the reward system that applies to employees. Every effort is made to achieve the goal, including by using human resources, namely reliable and professional workers, so that there is a maximum enthusiasm to achieve maximum work performance as well. It needs to be understood that human resources will determine the success or failure of an organization in achieving its stated goals. Allowances must be seen as part of the total compensation package offered to employees.

An organization or agency should have a good internal control system because if the organization does not have a good internal control system, it will cause fraud or deviation in carrying out its respective responsibilities. Prevention of fraud can be done by having a clear separation of tasks or functions between operational functions, authorization functions, and recording functions. With the elements of a good internal control system, it will make it easier for management to make decisions, and the effectiveness and efficiency of the organization can be achieved.

The provision of performance allowances to employees should receive primary attention from the leadership. The provision of sufficient performance allowances will have a positive influence on employee morale. This is a substitute for the contribution of energy or expertise that has been given by employees to the organization. The provision of benefits given to employees is based on grading or position and performance produced. The performance itself cannot be achieved optimally if benefits are given disproportionately (Ivancevich, 2008). While benefits themselves will not improve performance if employee satisfaction is not achieved, therefore job satisfaction can be a variable that influences the influence of benefits on performance.

Allowances are one form of rights obtained by civil servants, both civil servants and government employees with work agreements (PPPK). The provision of allowances and incentives is expected to improve the performance of civil servants towards a better and more professional direction. Through the provision of allowances, civil servants are more motivated to carry out their duties and obligations with enthusiasm and full loyalty. The allowances given to Civil Servants (PNS) must be accounted for by the employee so that they remain enthusiastic in carrying out their duties. According to the regulation of the Minister of Empowerment of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform Number 63 of 2011 concerning guidelines for the arrangement of the Civil Servant performance allowance system, it is stated that to improve employee performance in government agencies that have implemented bureaucratic reform, performance allowances need to be provided.

The provision of performance allowances to civil servants must be fair and appropriate, following the weight of the work and its responsibilities as well as the level (Index) of the cost of living in the area where the civil servant is. Job satisfaction reflects a

person's feelings towards their work, this is evident in the employee's positive attitude towards their work and everything they face in their work environment. The personnel or management department must always monitor job satisfaction because it affects absenteeism, employee turnover, job satisfaction, and other important issues. So in general, job satisfaction can be interpreted as something pleasant or unpleasant that employees view their work. So it can be concluded that job satisfaction is a person's feeling or attitude towards the work they do, which can be influenced by various factors, both internal and external factors.

Ganyang (2018) explains that job satisfaction is a feeling that employees have about their work, both in the form of pleasant and unpleasant feelings. By having job satisfaction in an employee at work, it will further spur their participation in every activity to achieve their goals, this is because of the individual behavior in the organization which is an interaction between individual characteristics and organizational characteristics. Meanwhile, Sutrisno (2019) states that job satisfaction is an employee's attitude towards work related to work situations, cooperation between employees, rewards received at work, and things related to physical and psychological factors.

Satisfaction is often associated as a result of employee motivation, such as the findings of Munandar & Prayekti (2020) stated that intrinsic motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This result is also supported by research by Khazamah et al (2021) that intrinsic motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction. This condition is also reinforced by research by Kurniawan et al (2021) which states that intrinsic motivation has a significant effect on employee job satisfaction.

Satisfaction is a reflection of employee behavior, work morale, discipline, and work performance. This satisfaction is greatly enjoyed at work, and outside of work, and is also combined inside and outside of work, thus creating motivation to always work hard and be militant. Employees who see their workplace developing and progressing rapidly will be motivated not to change jobs considering that with the development of the organization, their future will also be guaranteed. This means that when employees feel satisfied with their work, they tend to care more about the quality of their work and are more committed to the organization and have a higher retention rate and will generally be more productive.

This job satisfaction also represents the difference between employee expectations and experiences that they get from their work. The greater the difference between expectations and experiences (in this case, unfulfilled expectations), the greater the dissatisfaction. Employees can feel satisfaction in their work because there are factors that support it. Each employee has their way of achieving job satisfaction. Some are satisfied because their income is sufficient, working hours are flexible, the work environment is safe, the manager or leader is professional and understands the organizational situation well, and so on.

Job satisfaction is also closely related to the psychology of an employee. Employees who are happy and satisfied in a job are always motivated to contribute more. On the other hand, dissatisfied employees will become lethargic, make mistakes, and become a burden to the organization. Several factors determine job satisfaction, including opportunities for advancement and job

promotion, salary and benefits, job security, institutions and management, supervision and superiors, work environment, social aspects of work, and the job itself.

According to Luthans (2015), the characteristics of employees who show high job satisfaction are those who have work achievement achievements, better physical health, are more productive, learn tasks related to new jobs faster, have fewer work accidents, file fewer complaints and reduce stress levels. Therefore, it can be said that employees who experience high job satisfaction, in their work, can usually complete two jobs, but can complete four or more jobs in a day because they can achieve serious results.

Employee job satisfaction is also determined by a good boss/manager and co-workers who support each other. The attitude and behavior of the boss in leading certainly affect employee satisfaction in working, as well as the cooperative attitude of his co-workers and the work environment. Leadership implemented by a leader in an organization can create harmonious integration and encourage employees to achieve their goals optimally. Direction, attention, and motivation from the leader are expected to encourage employees to do their jobs well. If the leader or co-workers do not care about each other, the work environment is uncomfortable, the leadership is arbitrary and the organization does not seem to care about employees, then the work carried out will not run well and will cause problems and automatically job satisfaction will decrease. As the results of the initial observations of researchers in the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI), it was found that there were still employees in each department/section who felt dissatisfied with job promotions that did not match their work performance, were dissatisfied with the leadership model that only trusted certain employees to work, there were still employees who were often absent but did not receive punishment according to the laws and regulations of the State Civil Apparatus, and there were still other dissatisfactions that surrounded their employees, such as an uncomfortable work environment and inappropriate supervision/control.

This study uses intrinsic motivation because the strongest motivation is intrinsic motivation. After all, it is embedded directly within the employee. Through intrinsic motivation, employees are aware of their responsibilities and better work and are motivated to be enthusiastic about completing their work well. Work results due to awareness create good performance and employees will be aware that by having good performance, they will be able to meet their life needs. According to Waruwu (2018) influences employee performance. The intrinsic motivation referred to here is motivation that comes from within the employee himself, the results of the study show that the greater the intrinsic motivation an employee has, the better the employee's performance will be.

Literature Review

1. Employee Performance

Performance is a term derived from the word Job Performance or Actual Performance (work achievement or actual achievement achieved by someone). According to Mangkunegara (2013), the performance achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties is following the responsibilities given to him.

Mahsun (2009), stated that performance is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of an

activity/program/policy in realizing the goals, objectives, mission and vision of an organization as stated in the strategic planning of an organization. Gibson (2009), stated that a person's performance is determined by his ability and job satisfaction to carry out the work. Therefore, it is concluded that performance is the work achievement or work results (output) both in quality and quantity achieved by human resources per unit period in carrying out their work duties according to the responsibilities given to them.

Performance measurement according to Mathis (2006) which is an indicator in measuring employee performance or achievement is as follows:

- a) Quantity of work, namely the volume of work produced under normal conditions.
- b) Quality of work, which can be in the form of neatness, accuracy, and relevance of results without ignoring the volume of work.
- c) Punctuality, namely the use of work periods that are adjusted to company or government agency policies.
- d) Cooperation, namely the ability to handle relationships with others at work.

2. Performance Allowances

The definition of allowances according to Simamora (2004) is payments and services that protect and complement basic salary and the organization can pay all or part of these allowances. In the Big Indonesian Dictionary, the definition of allowances that are adjusted to this topic of discussion is additional income outside of salary as assistance or support.

Performance allowances are gifts (awards); and rewards. According to Dharma (2013), performance allowances are something that employees receive in return for the contributions they have made to the organization where they work. Performance allowances include all rewards, both in the form of money and goods, both routine and non-routine, and both those given directly and indirectly. Direct rewards for example: salary/wages, position allowances, special allowances, bonuses, and various types of assistance that are given routinely. Indirect rewards consist of facilities, health, pension funds, and disaster compensation.

Komaruddin (2006) stated that a performance allowance is a reward or reward, especially for services that have been used. The remuneration system must consider the rewards given to input and output in a balanced way. The input in question is how competent or qualified a person is in doing a job to achieve performance goals. Likewise with output, namely the suitability of work results with performance targets that must be achieved by the person in their work, compensation needs to be given if the person can achieve it.

Edison, et al., (2017) performance allowance indicators are divided into two, namely:

- a) Normative performance allowance. Normative performance allowance is the minimum performance allowance that must be received, consisting of salary or wages and fixed allowances such as health and holiday or religious allowances.
- b) Policy performance allowance. Policy performance allowance is a performance allowance that is based on policies and special considerations, such as professional allowances, meal

allowances, transportation allowances, bonuses, leave money, production services, and holidays.

3. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises after comparing perceptions or impressions of job satisfaction or work results. Meanwhile, Oliver (1998) defines satisfaction as the level of a person's feelings after comparing job satisfaction/perceived results with their expectations (Handoko, 2008). So, the level of satisfaction is a function of the difference between perceived job satisfaction and expectations. If job satisfaction is below expectations, employees will be disappointed, if job satisfaction is as expected, employees will be satisfied.

Employee job satisfaction must be created as well as possible so that employee morale, dedication, love and discipline increase. Job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that is pleasant and loves one's job. This attitude is reflected in work morale, discipline, and work performance. Job satisfaction is enjoyed in work, outside work and a combination of inside and outside work (Hasibuan; 2017)

According to Sutrisno (2017) the term "Satisfaction" refers to an individual's general attitude towards their work. A person with a high level of job satisfaction shows a positive attitude towards work. Satisfied employees will be able to work well, enthusiastically, and actively, and can perform better than employees who do not get job satisfaction. Employees who do not get job satisfaction will never achieve psychological satisfaction and will eventually have negative attitudes or behaviors and in turn, can cause frustration. Job satisfaction is an employee's attitude towards work related to work situations, cooperation between employees, rewards received from work, and things related to physical and psychological factors.

Several factors influence employee job satisfaction in an organization. Several experts have varying opinions regarding the factors that can influence employee job satisfaction. Sudaryo, Agus & Nunung (2018) said that job satisfaction can be influenced by several factors, including:

- a) Salary. namely, the amount of payment received by a person as a result of carrying out work, whether it is following needs and is felt to be fair
- b) The work itself. The work itself, namely the content of the work done by a person, whether it has satisfying elements
- c) Co-workers. Co-workers, namely friends with whom a person always interacts in carrying out work. A person can feel that their co-workers are very pleasant or unpleasant.
- d) Superiors. Superiors, namely someone who always gives orders or instructions in carrying out work
- e) Promotions. Promotions, namely the possibility that a person can develop through promotion.
- f) Work environment. Work environment, namely physical and non-physical environment. employees

3. Intrinsic Motivation

According to Robbins and Judge (2017), motivation is an effort made by individuals to achieve every goal in their lives, in the organizational realm motivation is the behavior of individuals who work with all their efforts due to certain factors to achieve organizational goals.

Meanwhile, according to Luthans (2011), motivation is a process as an initial step for someone to take action due to physical and psychological deficiencies, namely an encouragement aimed at meeting certain goals. Every employee who works in an organization must have the motivation to work to improve the performance of the organization.

Extrinsic motivation according to Fahmi (2016) is motivation that arises from outside a person, then encourages the person to build and grow a spirit of motivation within the person to change all attitudes they have towards the better.

Intrinsic motivation according to Suwatno (2011) is something that becomes active or the emergence of this drive is not influenced by external factors because every individual already has the drive to do something. Meanwhile, according to Luthans (2011), intrinsic motivation is motivation that arises grows, and

develops within the person, which then encourages them to do something valuable and meaningful.

Indicators of intrinsic motivation according to Robbins (2006) the indicators used are as follows:

- a) Appreciation
- b) Social relationships
- c) Life needs
- d) Success in work

Framework

This framework of thought explains the variable indicators used in the study. To get a clearer picture, the schematic influence between the independent variables on the dependent variable can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 1. Thinking Framework

Methods

The research was conducted at the Office of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI), Jalan MT Haryono Kav 52, Pancoran, South Jakarta 12770. The research was conducted from December 2023 to March 2024.

This research uses an explanatory analysis approach, namely each variable stated in the hypothesis is observed by testing the causal relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, as well as the mediating variable in this case is intrinsic motivation, as the observed variable can mediate the direct relationship of the independent variable (performance allowance and job satisfaction) to the dependent variable (employee performance). The influence of the mediating variable can strengthen or weaken the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. This phenomenon is created as a variable (X3), where intrinsic motivation is a mediating variable which will later be tested through an interaction test.

Population and Sample

In general, the population is meant as part of a generalization area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics, Sugiyono (2012:115). The population in this study were employees of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI), totaling 548 people.

According to Sugiyono (2012), samples are generally about part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. If the population is large and the author cannot study everything in the population due to limited funds, manpower, and time, then the author can use a sample taken from that population. What is learned from the sample, the conclusion will apply to the population. For that reason, samples taken from the population must be truly representative.

In this study, the determination of the number of samples taken came from employees at the Office of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI), using the formula from Yamane (1967). It is known that the population of employees at the Office of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI) is N = 548 people and the precision level set at d = 10%. Based on this formula, the number of samples obtained was 85 respondents.

Analysis Model

Descriptive analysis is an analysis method that aims to describe or explain something as it is (Irawan, 2004) in Baroroh (2008). In this study, data presentation uses a table of data analysis of average values (means) and frequency distributions Path analysis is an extension of multiple linear regression analysis, or path analysis is the use of regression analysis to estimate the causal relationship between variables (causal models) that have been previously determined based on theory (Ghozali, 2018). Regression analysis with intervening variables is used to determine the total.

Result

Figure 2. Result

1. The Effect of Performance Allowances and Job Satisfaction on Intrinsic Motivation

To find out this, it is necessary to use the F test. The following is a test of each variable:

Table 1. Results of the F Test of the Effect of Performance Allowances and Job Satisfaction on Intrinsic Motivation

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1155.316	2	577.658	806.518	.000 ^b
	Residual	58.731	82	.716		
	Total	1214.047	84			

a. Dependent Variable: X3

b. Predictors: (Constant), X2, X1

Source: Primary Data processed, 2024

The results of the F test for the variables of performance allowance and job satisfaction on intrinsic motivation obtained a calculated F value = 806.518 and an F-table of 3.95 with a significance value of 0.000. This means that F-calculate > F-table (806.518 > 3.95), and the sig value (0.000) < (0.05) which means that H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted. This provides the conclusion that performance allowance and job satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on intrinsic motivation. Thus, the first hypothesis is tested and proven.

2. The Effect of Performance Allowance and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

Table 2. Results of the F Test of the Effect of Performance Allowance and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1249.032	2	624.516	637.103	.000 ^b
	Residual	80.380	82	.980		
	Total	1329.412	84			

a. Dependent Variable: Y

b. Predictors: (Constant), X2, X1

Source: Primary Data processed, 2024

The results of the F test for the variables of performance allowance and job satisfaction on employee performance obtained a calculated F value = 637.103 and an F-table of 3.95 with a significance value of 0.000. This means that $F\text{-calculate} > F\text{-table}$ ($637.103 > 3.95$), and the sig value ($0.000 < (0.05)$) which means that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. This provides the conclusion that performance allowance and job satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Thus, the second hypothesis is tested and proven.

3. The Effect of Intrinsic Motivation on Employee Performance

To test the effect of intrinsic motivation on employee performance, a t-test is carried out. The following are the results of the t-test:

Table 3. Results of the T-test on the Effect of Intrinsic Motivation on Employee Performance

		Coefficients			
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t
1	(Constant)	4.680	1.760		2.660
	X3	.830	.070	.794	11.882
					Sig.
					.009
					.000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: Primary Data processed, 2024

The t-test results for the intrinsic motivation variable obtained a calculated t-value of 11,882 and a t-table of 1.666. This means that the calculated $t > t\text{-table}$ ($11.783 > 1.666$), and the sig value ($0.000 < (0.05)$) which means that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. This provides the conclusion that intrinsic motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Thus, the third hypothesis is tested and proven.

4. The Effect of Performance Allowances on Employee Performance Through Intrinsic Motivation

$$X_1 \rightarrow X_3 \rightarrow Y = (\rho_{x_3x_1}) \times (\rho_{yx_3}) = 0,533 \times 0,794 = 0,423$$

In the performance allowance variable, the indirect influence value is obtained from the path coefficient value $\rho_{x_3x_1}$ multiplied by the path coefficient value ρ_{yx_3} . The multiplication results show that the indirect influence coefficient value (0.423) is greater than the direct influence coefficient value (0.008), which means that H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted. This shows that intrinsic motivation has a positive and significant mediating effect on performance allowances and job satisfaction in influencing employee performance. Thus, hypothesis four is proven and not tested.

5. The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance Through Intrinsic Motivation

$$X_2 \rightarrow X_3 \rightarrow Y = (\rho_{x_3x_2}) \times (\rho_{yx_3}) = 0,603 \times 0,794 = 0,478$$

In the job satisfaction variable, the indirect influence value is obtained from the path coefficient value $\rho_{x_3x_1}$ multiplied by the path coefficient value ρ_{yx_3} . The multiplication results show that the indirect influence coefficient value (0.478) is smaller than the direct influence coefficient value (0.966), which means that H_0 is accepted and H_1 is rejected. This shows that intrinsic motivation does not have a positive effect and does not significantly mediate performance allowances and job satisfaction in influencing employee performance. Thus, the fifth hypothesis is not proven and not tested.

Discussion

1. The Effect of Performance Allowances and Job Satisfaction on Intrinsic Motivation in Employees of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI)

Based on the results of the descriptive analysis of the performance allowance variables, the indicators that dominate the formation of the performance allowance variables are policy performance allowances, in which BP2MI employees receive professional allowances according to their group and receive food allowances adjusted to their group. The average value of the performance allowance variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that the normative performance allowance and policy performance allowance indicators form the performance allowance variable.

In the job satisfaction variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the job satisfaction variable is salary, that the salary received by BP2MI employees is following their work and the salary received by BP2MI employees is following the risk of their work. The average value of the job satisfaction variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that the salary indicator, the work itself, coworkers, superiors, promotions, and the work environment form the job satisfaction variable.

In the intrinsic motivation variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the intrinsic motivation variable is the need for life, that BP2MI employees work according to the employee's workload and BP2MI employees work according to the established standards. The average value of the intrinsic motivation variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that indicators of appreciation, social relationships, need for life, and success in work form the intrinsic motivation variable. Based on the regression analysis, it shows that performance allowances and job satisfaction provide an increase in the intrinsic motivation of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI). The results of this study are in line with the results of research

conducted by I Ketut Andika Widyaputra, A.A. Sagung Kartika Dewi (2018); Indra Suryadi, Sugito Efendi (2018); Yoel Brando Sitopu, Kevin Arianda Sitinjak, Fenny Krisna Marpaung (2021); Muhammad Fikri Hakim, Muhammad Anhar, Dian Surya Sampurna (2020); Awali Prasetya Hanif, Sri Utami Ady (2022); Dewi Prawitasari, Harsono, and Harianto Respati (2022); Ade Fitriyana, Wawan Prahawian, Roni Kambara (2023).

2. The Effect of Performance Allowances and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI)

Based on the results of the descriptive analysis of the performance allowance variables, the indicator that dominates the formation of the performance allowance variables is the policy performance allowance, in BP2MI employees receive professional allowances according to their group and receive food allowances adjusted to their group. The average value of the performance allowance variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that the normative performance allowance and policy performance allowance indicators form the performance allowance variable.

In the job satisfaction variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the job satisfaction variable is salary, that the salary received by BP2MI employees is following their work and the salary received by BP2MI employees is following the risks of their work. The average value of the job satisfaction variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that salary indicators, the work itself, coworkers, superiors, promotions, and the work environment form job satisfaction variables.

In the employee performance variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the employee performance variable is punctuality, that BP2MI Employee Work is completed on time and BP2MI Employees have high work punctuality. The average value of the employee performance variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that indicators of work quality, work quantity, punctuality, and cooperation form employee performance variables. Based on the results of the regression analysis, show that performance allowances and job satisfaction provide an increase in the performance of employees of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI). The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Astaridiah Setianingsih, Nurul Matinni (2021); I Ketut Andika Widyaputra, A.A. Sagung Kartika Dewi (2018); Indra Suryadi, Sugito Efendi (2018); Yoel Brando Sitopu, Kevin Arianda Sitinjak, Fenny Krisna Marpaung (2021); Muhammad Fikri Hakim, Muhammad Anhar, Dian Surya Sampurna (2020); Awali Prasetya Hanif, Sri Utami Ady (2022); Dewi Prawitasari, Harsono, and Harianto Respati (2022); Ade Fitriyana, Wawan Prahawian, Roni Kambara (2023).

3. The Effect of Intrinsic Motivation on Employee Performance at the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI)

In the intrinsic motivation variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the intrinsic motivation variable is the need for life, that BP2MI employees work according to the employee's workload and BP2MI employees work according to the established standards. The average value of the intrinsic motivation variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree

that indicators of appreciation, social relationships, need for life, and success in work form the intrinsic motivation variable.

In the employee performance variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the employee performance variable is punctuality, that BP2MI employees' work is completed on time and BP2MI employees have high work punctuality. The average value of employee performance variables shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that indicators of work quality, work quantity, punctuality, and cooperation form employee performance variables. Based on the results of the regression analysis, shows that intrinsic motivation increases the performance of employees of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI). The results of the study show that it is in line with the research of Aminar Sutra Dewi, and Putri Wulandari (2022); and is not in line with the research of Raden Budi Satriyo (2019).

4. The Effect of Performance Allowances on Employee Performance at the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI) Through Intrinsic Motivation

Based on the results of the descriptive analysis of the performance allowance variables, the indicator that dominates the formation of the performance allowance variables is the policy performance allowance, in BP2MI employees receive professional allowances according to their group and receive food allowances adjusted to their group. The average value of the performance allowance variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that the normative performance allowance and policy performance allowance indicators form the performance allowance variable.

In the intrinsic motivation variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the intrinsic motivation variable is the need for life, that BP2MI employees work according to the employee's workload and BP2MI employees work according to the standards that have been set. The average value of the intrinsic motivation variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that the indicators of appreciation, social relations, life needs, and success in work form the intrinsic motivation variable.

In the employee performance variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the employee performance variable is punctuality, that BP2MI Employee Work is completed on time and BP2MI Employees have high work punctuality. The average value of the employee performance variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that indicators of work quality, work quantity, punctuality, and cooperation form employee performance variables. Based on the results of the path analysis, shows that intrinsic motivation has an impact on increasing performance allowances on the performance of employees of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI). The results of this study are in line with the research of I Ketut Andika Widyaputra, A.A. Sagung Kartika Dewi (2018); Indra Suryadi, Sugito Efendi (2018); Yoel Brando Sitopu, Kevin Arianda Sitinjak, Fenny Krisna Marpaung (2021); Muhammad Fikri Hakim, Muhammad Anhar, Dian Surya Sampurna (2020); Awali Prasetya Hanif, Sri Utami Ady (2022); Dewi Prawitasari, Harsono, and Harianto Respati (2022); Ade Fitriyana, Wawan Prahawian, Roni Kambara (2023).

6. *The Effect of Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI) Through Intrinsic Motivation*

In the job satisfaction variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the job satisfaction variable is salary, that the salary received by BP2MI employees is following their work and the salary received by BP2MI employees is following the risk of their work. The average value of the job satisfaction variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that the indicators of salary, the work itself, coworkers, superiors, promotions and the work environment form the job satisfaction variable.

In the intrinsic motivation variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the intrinsic motivation variable is the need for life, that BP2MI employees work according to the employee's workload and BP2MI employees work according to the standards that have been set. The average value of the intrinsic motivation variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that the indicators of appreciation, social relationships, life needs, and success in work form the intrinsic motivation variable.

In the employee performance variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the employee performance variable is punctuality, that BP2MI Employee Work is completed on time and BP2MI Employees have high work punctuality. The average value of the employee performance variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that indicators of work quality, work quantity, punctuality, and cooperation form employee performance variables. Based on the results of the path analysis, show that intrinsic motivation does not have an impact on increasing job satisfaction on the performance of employees of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI). The results of this study are not in line with the research of I Ketut Andika Widyaputra, A.A. Sagung Kartika Dewi (2018); Indra Suryadi, Sugito Efendi (2018); Yoel Brando Sitopu, Kevin Arianda Sitinjak, Fenny Krisna Marpaung (2021); Muhammad Fikri Hakim, Muhammad Anhar, Dian Surya Sampurna (2020); Awali Prasetya Hanif, Sri Utami Ady (2022); Dewi Prawitasari, Harsono, and Harianto Respati (2022); Ade Fitriyana, Wawan Prahawan, Roni Kambara (2023).

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study on the Influence of Performance Allowances and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance Through Intrinsic Motivation at the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI), the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Based on the results of the descriptive analysis of the performance allowance variables, the indicator that dominates the formation of the performance allowance variables is the policy performance allowance, in which BP2MI employees receive professional allowances according to their group and receive food allowances adjusted to their group. The average value of the performance allowance variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that the normative performance allowance and policy performance allowance indicators form the performance allowance variable.
2. In the job satisfaction variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the job satisfaction variable is salary, that the salary received by BP2MI employees is

following their work and the salary received by BP2MI employees is following the risks of their work. The average value of the job satisfaction variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that the salary indicators, the work itself, coworkers, superiors, promotions, and work environment form the job satisfaction variable.

3. In the intrinsic motivation variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the intrinsic motivation variable is the need for life, that BP2MI employees work according to the employee's workload and BP2MI employees work according to the standards that have been set. The average value of the intrinsic motivation variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that indicators of appreciation, social relationships, need for life, and success in work form the intrinsic motivation variable.
4. In the employee performance variable, the indicator that gives the greatest value to the formation of the employee performance variable is punctuality, that BP2MI employees' work is completed on time and BP2MI employees have high work punctuality. The average value of the employee performance variable shows that BP2MI employees tend to agree that indicators of work quality, work quantity, punctuality, and cooperation form the employee performance variable.

Based on regression analysis and path analysis, it shows that:

1. Based on regression analysis, it shows that performance allowances and job satisfaction provide an increase in the intrinsic motivation of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI).
2. Based on the results of the regression analysis, show that performance allowances and job satisfaction provide an increase in the performance of employees of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI).
3. Based on the results of the regression analysis, show that intrinsic motivation provides an increase in the performance of employees of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI).
4. Based on the results of the path analysis, shows that intrinsic motivation has an impact on increasing performance allowances on the performance of employees of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI).
5. Based on the results of the path analysis, show that intrinsic motivation does not have an impact on increasing job satisfaction on the performance of employees of the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI).

Suggestions

Based on the results of the study on the Influence of Performance Allowances and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance Through Intrinsic Motivation at the Indonesian Migrant Workers Protection Agency (BP2MI), several suggestions can be submitted as follows:

1. The results of this study are expected to contribute to the development of scientific knowledge, insight, and experience of researchers in the field of human resource management, especially related to the theory of performance allowances, work discipline, intrinsic motivation and job satisfaction.
2. The results of this study are expected to provide input and references for BP2MI in improving employee job satisfaction through motivation, so that organizational performance can increase, especially for the BP2MI Office so that it can consider, design and implement effective and efficient human

resource management in achieving organizational goals and objectives, to improve by considering the following:

- a. Performance Allowance. It is a concern for the BP2MI Leadership, to pay attention to the normative performance allowance indicators that provide the lowest value for the formation of performance allowance variables, namely by providing bonuses or performance incentives in addition to getting allowances and health allowances for Employees with a health ceiling adjusted to the group.
- b. Job Satisfaction. To be a concern for BP2MI Leaders, to pay attention to the indicators of the work itself that give the lowest value to the formation of job satisfaction variables, namely by BP2MI leaders must motivate BP2MI Employees to like their jobs and always be committed to their tasks.
- c. Intrinsic Motivation. To be a concern for BP2MI Leaders, to pay attention to the reward indicators that give the lowest value to the formation of intrinsic motivation variables, namely by BP2MI leaders must pay attention to BP2MI Employees so that they are always enthusiastic about working by giving rewards so that BP2MI Employees are committed to their tasks.
- d. Employee Performance. To be a concern for BP2MI Leaders, to pay attention to the indicators of work quality that give the lowest value to the formation of employee performance variables, namely by leaders must pay attention to BP2MI Employees must have very high work quality by providing work incentives so that BP2MI Employees have high work standards.

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